

Campus and Creation in Côte d'Ivoire: Issues and Strategies for an Aesthetic of Camouflage in Zouglou

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Abstract

The history and origin of zouglou creations show that when texts are considered together as a group and in relation to the conditions of their production, they require the listener or reader to be part of an inner circle, which at the level of the communication process means they must contribute to creating the texts' meanings by using codes that guarantee their cohesion and coherence beyond any superficial interpretation. This article thus aims to decode the literary issues brought about through these processes by exploring what these processes say about the communities and groups that adopt them (here, Ivorian students). This article examines the mechanisms by which spoken campus "language" is able to convey the meaning of thought through the organisation and materialisation of information already present in the mind of each individual and informed listener or reader.

Keywords: zouglou, censorship, creation, creativity, image, ideology, Côte d'Ivoire

Introduction

In 1990, Côte d'Ivoire experienced an unprecedented social and political crisis that can be summarised as follows:

The economy is on hold, unemployment has reached intolerable levels, there is a shortage of money in state coffers and people's pockets. The hospitals, which are increasingly dilapidated, lack equipment, the schools, overcrowded, are turning everyone away, citizens' rights are being violated. (Séry 1990, 2)

It was against this backdrop and thanks to a commonplace university campus power cut on the night before exams that the political landscape would transform into an unprecedented inferno in Côte d'Ivoire. After weeks of increasingly widespread strikes and union demands, the government at the time conceded to multipartyism following three decades of single-party rule.

At the same time, people discovered zouglou, a practice that, according to one of its pioneers is “the expression of a form of behaviour and way of thinking through movement”.¹ Originating in student “*cités*”,² zouglou would gradually be established as a principally urban, popular protest movement. Combining dance, music and speech, zouglou productions were characterised by their persistent satire, urging everything to be criticised through ridicule and irony. Generally evolving and developing based on codes that were deliberately conveyed to the audience, the first zouglou songs were produced “in the heat of the moment” against the backdrop of the shifting political and social landscape. They drew on commonplace, trivial, mainstream events to establish a power that enabled them to intervene in reality and gain illocutionary strength. Inscribing the contextual situation of the speaker and interlocutor in factors determining the stylistic consistencies that created the special features of these practices, these texts that are received and claimed by symbolic force fields present in the context of their execution (Sarfati 2001, 28). *The* discourse/words in zouglou then become a place of investment that transforms the act of speaking, thus positioned, into literary fact. Indeed, although it may appear that the language used is uncomplicated, it is evident that these productions display the qualities of any literary text.

This article intends to examine the way in which zouglou is expressed and carries meaning both on university campus spaces and beyond, based on the fact that – in these creations that alert the imagination – in most cases, it is the contextual environment that makes the structures governing textual production come into existence for the reader-listener. What catches our attention is that we see something unfolding in these creations that Olivier Reboul describes as “the fundamental power of the metaphor” (1980, 128).

The article begins with a brief history of the genre and is followed by analysis of a corpus of texts, performances and interviews. Its approach is in line with the theory of discourse semantics and, more precisely, with the semantics of utterances. The basic premise is that any approach to a stylistic fact must endeavour, first and foremost, to define the places of its manifestation. By thus relating speech to social places and institutional settings, this analysis

aims to go beyond the text/context opposition to better understand zouglou as a form of expression consisting of both dance and highly literary speech.³

Between Words, Beyond the Sentence: Constructing an Image in Zouglou

In the 1980s, 20 years after many African nations gained independence, Côte d'Ivoire was under single-party rule. Community and politics were characterised by a lack of any sort of platform for free and open discussion. In addition, while swift economic growth ensued in the days and weeks immediately following independence, it was not long before the first economic difficulties arose in Côte d'Ivoire. The youth suffered the repercussions. It was against this backdrop that "Ambiance Facile" (Easy Atmosphere), the precursor to zouglou, emerged in *collèges* and *lycées* (lower and upper secondary schools), expressing a continually declining social reality:

During encounters with the OISSU,⁴ we parodied traditional songs to try and describe our problems in the *lycées*. Whether it was a supervisor being criticised because he was too mean, or a teacher being mocked.⁵

Sometimes when you're in the bus and you hear the others, they [the leaders] sing songs where you can't quite make out the words. One thing's for sure, it gives the bus a bit of atmosphere ... But once the bus has passed through the school gates, they start to shout out and then you can clearly hear the words of the genre "*Soro ô anango⁶ tchè.*"⁷

So, to explain, Soro was a teacher at the *lycée* who was well known for being extremely strict. He had ethnic scarification on his face like the Anango people, originally from Nigeria. To some extent then, through mockery and other jibes, pupils were avenging the bullying he made them suffer. However, they never dared to do so openly or to his face. Hence, when the buses were inside the school gates, in a place of censorship, the singers would mumble their words to make them inaudible and undecipherable, at least to the uninitiated. In this way, only those who frequented this limited inner circle – or had the codes to enter it – would receive the whole message, at least while within the school environment. It was only in stadiums, outside the school, that this criticism was more overt.

It can thus be maintained that Ambiance Facile, a movement from which zouglou is derived, did not take on its true meaning in these acts of verbal jousting and playful musical expression; this was just a simple smokescreen. Hence, this movement should be considered

in two different ways. In fact, in view of the methods used to communicate *Ambiance Facile*, it is clear that the movement – which had not yet become *zouglou* – did not exist just to liven up the local neighbourhood or entertain at football matches. It was established by the pupils themselves during extracurricular activities (trips out, *fêtes*, sports tournaments organised by the Office Ivoirien des Sports Universitaires (Ivorian Office for University Sports)), and groups would produce parodies of local songs through which they could evoke aspects of school life. *Ambiance Facile* therefore took *Wôyô*⁸ and its playfulness and added other ingredients, with the aim of:

- amusing players and supporters during journeys from the *lycées* and *collèges* to sporting events;
- galvanising the public and distracting their attention from the competition itself (a way to relieve the stress and tension caused by the competition) and, if necessary, to take pressure away from the athletes; and
- criticising the school system while diverting supervisors' attention by putting seemingly benign words to the rhythm, upon which other – often subversive and more or less inaudible – words were grafted.

In truth, the groups' exploits served as an initial platform for freedom of speech and for the circumvention of censorship. By removing all inhibitions, it thus seems that a *maquis* (in the military sense) aesthetic was developed in these parallel and transitory spaces. In a system where repression annihilated all vague hope of protest, the groups' strategy was to use these platforms as the only spaces that would give them the freedom to criticise. By moving the space for conflict to where it could not be heard, the singer destroyed any possibility of censorship by their adversary.

At this time, there were elections for new committee presidents in the university *cités*. Although not a student, Didier Bilé was called in to back up a candidate. The reason for this choice was simple: his ability to improvise and his mastery of *Ambiance Facile* techniques attracted crowds during lightning-quick passages, and that would be a major asset. He subsequently became a student himself and it was not unusual to see him performing alongside union leaders as part of a struggle in which his primary function was as a foil, helping to communicate the message of a union silenced by single-party rule and prevented from expressing itself freely and openly. And, to a large extent, these performances would

continue to function in the same way even when zouglou was introduced to the practice. Bilé describes his first few hours as a zouglou militant:

I remember I was there at the start, behind the first strike, the biggest strike; but I wasn't a unionist, though I had bizarre⁹ meetings with these people, just there to say: "There you go, as no one wants to let us speak, you do a zouglou performance, at this time, and we'll come and we'll speak." And that's what it was like. We started with "Gboglo Koffi",¹⁰ and the people replied "Oya iyo". [He sings:]¹¹

Gboglo Koffi / **Oya iyo** / Gboglo
Koffi / **Oya iyo** / On veut plus ça ô /
Oya iyo / Demain on va au campus /
Oya iyo / On va au campus / **Oya**
iyoy / On va dire à Zinsou ô / **Oya iyo**
/ On n'a plus d'argent pour manger /
Oya iyo ...

Gboglo Koffi / **Oya iyo** / Gboglo
Koffi / **Oya iyo** / Don't want it no
more oh / **Oya iyo** / Tomorrow
we're on campus / **Oya iyo** / We'll
be on campus / **Oya iyo** / We're
gonna to tell Zinsou¹² oh / **Oya iyo** /
We've no more cash for food / **Oya**
iyoy ...

With tree branches, we tapped on windows at three o'clock, four o'clock in the morning. At five o'clock the whole *cité* was up; the movement spread everywhere across the *cité*.¹³

It was under these conditions that Didier Bilé, former frontman of the *Ambiance Facile* group at the Grand-Bassam *lycée*, where he used to be a pupil, released a record featuring the protest song quoted above, and he did so with a group of students from the university *cité* in Yopougon (where events started that would snowball, affecting the whole country). Taking classics from the *Ambiance Facile* movement or improvising based on well-known songs, this group exposed the difficulties of student life, using their performances to make casual digs at academic and political leaders, all with a hint of humour and in a somewhat codified language.

However, it should be noted that now their criticism was enriched by a philosophical dimension that the pioneers continually incorporated into their protests and demands. They would give a name to their practice: zouglou – a polysemous term referring, they said, to both a philosophical attitude and dance steps.

Zouglou ... is the expression, through movement, of profound thought, of our demands ... the philosophy of struggle. That is why zouglou is not a wazari¹⁴ dance ... And the songs must raise our issues.¹⁵

In terms of issues, there were problems regarding accommodation and the sharing of residential space on campus, but that was not all.¹⁶

We were piled up, one on top of the other, we called our other friends Cambodians; they were the people squatting in rooms. Why Cambodians? Because in Vietnam, as you'll have seen, people would go out at night to fight. The next morning, they were all peasants. You didn't know who was who. These guys didn't have the right to stay in the *cités*, so they hid so they could sleep, and in the morning, they were all students, the visitors. They were called Cambodians ... Why were we called the parents? The country's only university was intended for 7,000 students but hosted 21,000. People who did their bac [baccalaureate examination] in Korhogo [in the far north of the country], when they weren't put up in student accommodation, since there wasn't enough, what did we want them to do? Let them end up on the street? We didn't need to know who they were, where they came from. There was no fear. It was: "OK, come with me, you have your mattress, you go there, and then that's it." We would all sleep together. In the morning, we had to go to class, we tidied away all the mattresses, that's why we were called campus parents, to clearly show we were brothers one and all, that we cared for each other, that we lived in solidarity for a start. And that was one of the great strengths in the birth of zouglou, one of Yopougon *cité*'s great strengths. We were very united. It was this situation, this way of life that would be highlighted by "Gboglo Koffi", the first zouglou song to come out of the student environment.¹⁷

The recurrent difficulties that governed their life in the *cité* cemented their community and also determined their way of being and thinking, acting and speaking:

We have a way of speaking: for example, we know that Goukouni Ouedeye had a beard, so when we saw a guy with a beard, we actually said Goukouni. [He laughs.] It was about images, it was full of imagery. And, for example, you needed to have experienced a certain situation; we didn't approve words just like that, the event needed to be quite well known across campus, among parents even, so people would approve. For example, when we say, "*l'homme, il a fait en Domi*" [the man did it in the Domi]

that's because we knew there was a girl in the *cit* called Dominique who had an incontinence problem, and who had ... on herself. So we say "*l'homme, il va en Domo*" [the man's going to the Domo – he's having a shit]. So the word was dependent on the event, on the form, on the size of the event.

... There were consequences afterwards, on the street, people used certain words taken from Nouchi,¹⁸ about experiences we knew to be political or social ... So, that's what it was like; they were expressions ... and if you weren't a student, you couldn't work out the meaning.¹⁹

Zouglou utterances spread in this way, thanks to a general feeling of belonging and mutual recognition on which meaning was constructed. Nevertheless, zouglou was not the only practice to function in this way, nor was it the first. The development of this type of expression was common practice within the student environment rather than being unique to this particular genre. In fact, as far back as we can recall, students in Cte d'Ivoire have expressed themselves using codes specific to their environment. Indeed, it was at the start of the 1970s that we saw the first traces of this practice emerge from the official orchestra of the University of Abidjan, grandiosely called OUA, the same acronym as the Organisation de l'Unit d'Africaine (Organisation of African Unity).

Au campus y avait presque plus
d'tudiants / Ds l'annonce du

l'oxygne / Mais avec qui danser
...²⁰

Kouadio mourant / Monsieur Kalet
/ Voyez nous n'avons plus de bl /
Et ainsi nous sommes tous tombs /
Pour aller  Cocody / Personne
n'osait arrter d'taxi / Filles et
garons empruntent le Maquis /
Allons aux palmiers /
Personnellement je mange  credit /
La situation n'tait pas meilleure 
Yop city / Conseils nationaux /
Rveillrent Kouadio / tudiants /
On va aller danser / Danser 

On campus there were scarcely any
 students / Since the news that
Kouadio died / Mr Kalet²¹ / See,
 we've no more dough / And so we're
 all too broke / To go to Cocody / No
 one dared stop a taxi / Girls and boys
 follow the Maquis / Let's go to

palmiers²² / Personally, I eat on
 credit / The situation's no better in
 Yop city / National councils / Woke
 up Kouadio / Students / We're going
 to dance / Dance at oxygen²³ / But
 dance with who ...

In this song denouncing the deterioration of student living conditions following the suspension of grant payments due to the crisis, numerous referents directly touch on university life, so students recognise themselves in the song without the need for further explanation. Complicity then follows, a feeling of collusion between the singer and the audience, thus creating a community. One lexeme deserves particular attention: “Kouadio”. This is a proper noun referring to the person responsible for the payment of student grants and is highlighted in bold in the extract above. However, over the course of time, this proper noun no longer referred to the individual but to the grant itself, and then to the payment counter. Hence, Kouadio = university grant, but also Kouadio = place for grant payment. So, phrases common to that environment include “I picked up my Kouadio” and “I’m going to the Kouadio.”

Through contextualisation, distortion and lexical misappropriation, it is thus possible to see the matrix emerge on which these practices are constructed. Much more than simple shifts in meaning (nor are they, strictly speaking, a case of metonymic functioning), the process by which a word changes sense owing to the particular context in which it was created and from which it draws its meaning has a very literary significance; this will be explored later. In addition, it is worth noting that, over time, the prevalence of a particular context that takes effect – and through which the word derives meaning – would become the distinctive feature of all creations originating from this student environment and especially from zouglou. In 1991, it could be seen in the movement’s protest song, “Gboglo Koffi” from Didier Bilé and Les Parents du Campus (Campus Parents):

Savez-vous / savez-vous / Ici en cité
 / La vie est dure / On a trop de
 problèmes / Pour avoir **N'daya** / Il
 faut bosser beaucoup / N'daya qui

est là / Ça suffit pas / Avec N'daya /
 On doit payer bouquins / On doit
 payer la chambre / On doit payer
 tickets / On doit faire photocopies /

Avec **cambodgien** / Si tu brèkes une
go / Ce sont des problèmes / Un
étudiant / Rencontre une go / Il lui
dit / Je suis étudiant / La go ne croit
pas / Mais tout en parlant / Il laisse
tomber sa carte / La go est **brisée** /
Elle lui demande / Où on s'en va? /
Parce que à Port-Bouët / Ce sont des
poètes / A Vridi / Ils sont radicaux /
Au campus / Ce sont des bluffeurs /
A Abobo / Ils ont beaucoup d'argent
/ A Mermoz / Ils ont des gos! /
“Quand on est en pointage on écrase
sur les dépenses. / “On prend un taxi,
et on **libère** en cité! / “Mais quand le
compteur fait clic / “Le cœur fait
clac ... / il lui dit: On va à Yop là / A
Yop city / Là-bas c'est le zouglou / **I
nan zouglou kata** / Ils arrivent en
chambre / Dans la chambre / Y'a des
cambodgiens / Mais est-ce que vous
savez / Ce qu'on appelle
cambodgien? / Les cambodgiens /
Ce sont des étudiants / Qui n'ont pas
droit à la chambre / On sait pas trop
ô / “Oh toi! / Parfois pour une
chambre prévue pour un / On se
retrouve à quatre. / Dans la cuisine,
y'a deux dormeurs. / Si c'est une
chambre double, on est parfois sept /
C'est ça les vraies réalités
estudiantines ... / Il arrive qu'au dix-
neuf du mois / L'étudiant se retrouve
sans ticket / Il va chez le voisin: /

Oh! **Parent!** Est-ce que je peux avoir
un ticket avec toi? Pitié! / Écrase
hein! Tu te **brises**, ça réussit pas / Il
va jusqu'au bâtiment des filles: / Oh!
Parente! Pitié! **Libère** un ticket sur
un frère! Le ventre est en wazari / –
Enfin, c'est le dernier, mais allons
quand même / Au restau, c'est **only
for dog** / On n'aime pas / On va
manger quand même / On n'a pas
l'argent ... / Je vous ai pas parlé des
cars / Pour aller aux cours le matin /
Les Cars sont bourrés! / Y'a un
adage qui dit en milieu estudiantin /
Que la galanterie s'arrête à la porte
des cars / Si tu vois les gos **soigner**
jusqu'au campus! / Oh! Mais
vraiment ça fait pitié! / En amphï,
c'est même pareil / Identique! / Ce
sont les mêmes problèmes. / Quoi
qu'on dise, vous n'y pouvez rien /
Donc nous on fait quoi? / On danse
le zouglou / **i nan zouglou kata.**

Do you know / do you know / Here
in the *cit* / Life is tough / We’ve too
many problems / To have **N’daya** /
We have to work lots / N’daya that’s
there / Is not enough / With N’daya /
We have to pay for books / We have
to pay for a room / We have to pay
for **tickets**²⁴ / We have to do
photocopies / With **Cambodian** / If
you **brkes**²⁵ a **go** / These are the
problems / A student / Meets a go /
He says / I am a student / The go
doesn’t believe him / But while
speaking / He drops his card / The go
is **brise** / She asks him / Where are
we going? / Because in Port-Bout /
They are poets / In Vridi / They are
radicals / On campus / They are
bluffers / In Abobo / They have lots
of money / In Mermoz / They have
gos! / “When we are **en pointage**²⁶
we blow the cash. / “We take a taxi,
and we **libre** the *cit*! / “But when
the counter goes click / “The heart
goes clack ... / He tells her: We’re
going to Yop / To Yop city / That’s
where you find zougrou / **I nan**
zougrou kata / They get to the
bedroom / In the bedroom /
Cambodians are there / But do you
know / Who are called Cambodians?
/ Cambodians / Are students / Who
aren’t entitled to a room / We don’t

really know oh / “²⁷Oh you! /
Sometimes in a room meant for one /
We end up as a four. / In the kitchen,
there are two sleepers. / If it’s a
double room, sometimes there are
seven of us / These are genuine
student realities ... / Sometimes on
the nineteenth of the month / The
student ends up without a ticket / He
goes to his neighbour: / Oh! **Parent!**
Can I have a ticket with you? Have
pity! / Drop it, eh! You **brises**, it
doesn’t work / He goes over to the
girls’ block: / Oh! **Parente!** Have
pity! **Libre** a ticket to a brother!
My stomach is in a **wazari**²⁸/ – Well,
it’s the last one, but let’s go anyway
/ To the restau, it’s **only for dog**²⁹ /
We don’t like it / We’ll eat it all the
same / We don’t have money ... / I
told you about the buses / Going to
lessons in the morning / The buses
are packed! / There’s an adage that
says that with students / Chivalry
stops at the bus door / If you see the
gos **soigner** going to campus! / Oh!
That’s such a shame! / In the lecture
hall, it’s just the same / Identical! /
It’s the same old problems. / No
matter what’s said, there’s nothing
you can do / So what do we do? / We
dance zougrou / **i nan zougrou kata.**

In this song, the very first for the movement (at least officially), the words in bold are all motivated by the context from which they take their real meaning. In the notes and below, some of these terms are explained and their uses explored.

N'daya is the name of a charitable organisation created by the wife of the first Ivorian president, Félix Houphouët-Boigny, who was in post at the time the song came out. He was harshly criticised by young students, whose historical 1990 uprising led to the creation of a multiparty system to replace the single-party system that had been all-powerful until that point. His wife's association aimed to help disadvantaged children, but it was accused by public opinion of carrying out activities with money from state coffers. As a result, N'daya now refers to the help that the state gives to students who originally did not have a grant but are deemed deserving thanks to their grades. Equivalent to half a grant, this help is seen as ludicrous, just like the assistance apparently given by the first lady to supposed underprivileged children.

It is important to know that, from start to finish, the song features a refrain – with mockery in the background – announcing the international year of the child who deserved, it seemed, the creation of this association.

Parent relates to the idea of solidarity that created so-called “Cambodians” on campus, and this term also refers to students. And in the same spirit, the verb *soigner* (to care for) in the phrase “*si tu vois les gos soigner dans le car*” (if you see the girls caring in the bus) is a similarity observed between two situations: the first being the medical student (intern) standing over a sick person, and the second being a passenger standing on a bus due to lack of seats, who consequently ends up in the same position as the trainee medic, so *soigner* here means “in a standing position”, owing to this shared experience and going beyond that which is ordinarily signified by language. Through the addition of meaning that is somewhat disjointed from the words of language, the zouglou utterance is fundamentally inscribed in group rationale, which delineates a border between a united us and them. In this regard, the neuralgic threshold that opens up to the surge of meaning no longer clings just to language – or rather to the ethnos – it necessarily infers a cultural community that alone guarantees a valid interpretation.

For example, this is the case with the verb *libérer* (to liberate), a substitute word which throughout the song means either “to make way towards” (we liberate the *cité*) or “to give”

(liberate a ticket to a brother). In other circumstances, it can mean “to dance”, and more specifically to dance zouglou. We will see in the developments that follow that in a student environment, the word *libérer* rather than *danser* is used, the expression here referring only to dancing zouglou: we liberate zouglou.

The term *brisée* (from “*briser*”, meaning to break, shatter or smash) is also polysemous in this context. It first means to be seduced – the *go* (girl) is *brisée* (broken) – while later it indicates failure: *Tu te brises* (you break yourself). Indeed, in this last example, it is evident that outside the sentence, it is very much the context preceding the enunciation that governs the emergence of meaning. The identification and the deciphering of values inferred by this usage presupposes shared knowledge on the part of the receiver, thus allowing the discourse to make sense, largely on the basis of implicit and indisputable evidence. This is the case in the phrase *I nan zouglou kata* (literally, let’s dance kata zouglou). On this last, seemingly perfunctory, note that ends a long litany of student disappointments, it feels as if the singer is inviting you to dance, which clearly acts as a life-saving release, but markedly has more subversive intentions. The following section endeavours to show that, while zouglou dancing could initially bring about the feeling of choreographic instinct devoid of linguistic meaning, the practice proves to be more complex, owing to the expressiveness that is extricated from it.

The Zouglou of Student Pioneers: Speaking Dance, Coded Dance

Zouglou emerged from the university *cit* in Yopougon, a district located in the northern suburb of Abidjan in Cte d’Ivoire. While the practice borrows from another street genre, Wy, its musical forms and terminology would have been forged long before. In fact, all versions of the story agree that the word “zouglou” was first used by two friends, well before they started at university, to joke about the general appearance of a young woman to whom they gave the alias “*zouglou bi*”. The term *bi* comes from Bete, a national language, and is used to refer to someone you love, but the word *zouglou* changes its meaning to lack of grace, deformity or even ugliness. Over the course of its usage, the word *bi* was dropped and *zouglou* became an adverb of manner. “*Tu fais en zouglou*” (you are doing it the zouglou way) then meant that you do unattractive things. In the minds of astute listeners, the term then referred to any mad situation, conveying meaning through notice of the context of its first use.

Subsequently, these two partners in crime started to do dance steps that imitated a particular philosophy lecturer's body movements, which were quite chaotic and not very attractive, and they became part of zouglou's caricatural rationale. The removal of the term *béi* demonstrated here the widening of the concept and its application to fields other than those that are physical.

Stemming from this initial base, and around these two friends, new steps and movements were introduced on campus to describe the students' struggles against adversity for which there is no solution other than to appeal for divine mercy.

“Ah! La vie estudiantine!

“Ah! Student life!

Elle est belle!

It's wonderful!

“Mais on y rencontre beaucoup de problèmes.

“But we've faced many problems

“Lorsqu'on voit un étudiant

“When you see a student

“On l'envie: toujours bien sapé,

“You're jealous: always smart

“Joli garçon sans produits ghanéens.

“Pretty boy, nothing from Ghana.

“Mais en fait, il faut rentrer dans son milieu, pour Connaître la misère et la galère de l'étudiant.

“But really, you need to see his space to

Understand the student's misery and pain.

“Ô bon Dieu!

“Oh good God!

“Qu'avons-nous fait pour subir un tel sort?

“What have we done to suffer such fate?

“Et c'est cette manière d'implorer le Seigneur qui a engendré le zouglou

“And it's this way of begging the Lord that spawned zouglou

“Danse philosophique qui permet à l'étudiant de se recueillir et d'oublier un peu ses problèmes

“A philosophical dance that helps students pull themselves together and forget their problems a bit

“So let’s dance zouglou!

Zouglou dancing thus displayed all the features of a coded language, and the university crisis of 1990 contributed towards the acceleration of the codification and diversification of that language, the focal point always being its ugliness, which acquired a metaphysical dimension. As an active interaction, zouglou thus conveyed a process of transformation that adhered to the triadic structure of African orality, inasmuch as it departed from the actor (the group of students) to the recipient (the rest of society) through the intermediary of an agent (the dancer) gifted with meaningful movements. In this process, the students’ words were revealed, rather like the speaking and poetic dances of the Akan people of Côte d’Ivoire and Ghana.³⁰ As in Saussurean linguistic theory, the word is affected by a sonorous mass from which it takes its meaning. Similarly here, movement is manifested as a gestural mass of words through which dance then becomes the carrier of the word, and “forms thought through movement” (Adom 2013):

Zouglou movements are not movements that happen by chance. They are movements that are thoughts before being translated gesturally through dance ... That’s why in zouglou, we don’t say dancing, but liberating. This is because we have accumulated so much negative energy, so many problems, and to liberate some of that negative energy, we are always in zouglou mode. We liberate through zouglou. We have a particular way of dancing. We go from low down to up high, to show we’re struggling on the ground, we’re looking to escape ... then, tired, we raise our heads, and ask: Lord, where are you?³¹

A dancer performs the original basic zouglou moves as follows: jerky, quick steps, their hands spread out, before wiping the forehead to show fatigue and despair, and then their hands form the shape of a visor, seeking transcendental help. Finally, both hands are brought to the face, the left in the right, palms open and raised towards the sky, by way of prayer. Zouglou movement then becomes a metaphor for the ugliness of its origins in all its forms; more than anything, it is a manifestation of social deformity expressed both in the dancers’ poses and the different zouglou moves and gestures.

In addition to the basic moves, and related to the different contexts of their execution, different forms of zouglou emerged: *zouglou militaire* (military zouglou),³² *zouglou caillou* (stone zouglou),³³ *zouglou kata* (kata zouglou)³⁴ and more. So many variants, all of which

position zouglou dance as a genuine expressive form, translatable into a clear and expressive linguistic discourse. Zouglou dance thus expanded and doubled up as a verbal discourse that, by means of the body in its entirety, won back spaces of freedom.

“Si tu vois les gos soigner jusqu’au campus!	“If you see the gos ³⁶ soigner ³⁷ going to campus!
“Oh! Mais vraiment ça fait pitié!	Oh! That’s such a shame!
“En amphi, c’est même pareil	In the lecture hall, it’s just the same
“Identique! Ce sont les mêmes problèmes.	Identical! It’s the same old problems.
“Quoi qu’on dise, vous n’y pouvez rien	No matter what’s said, there’s nothing you can do
“Donc nous on fait quoi?	So what do we do?
“On danse le zouglou	We dance zouglou
I nan zouglou wôyô	I nan zouglou wôyô
...	...
Marcel:	Marcel ³⁸ :
Viens danser!	Come dance!
Danser le zouglou avec nous	Dance zouglou with us
I nan zouglou kata ³⁵	I nan zouglou kata

While the ending of this extract is an invitation to dance, something heard frequently in early zouglou but also in many traditional and modern songs in Côte d’Ivoire, the contextual articulation leading to the emergence of the lexical unit “*zouglou kata*” indicates that this performed movement seeks to unveil a hidden thought. In fact, “*zouglou kata*” requires the choreographic reprise of a karate move that a student grappling with a soldier during a raid

(there were many at the time) would have performed against his adversary. The invitation to dance then is like a metaphor for a battle call because the reference to *zouglou kata* evokes the upper hand that, in times of prior adversity, these same students were able to have over their supposed adversaries (who may have been the most violent representation of the state's power during the single-party system).

Since then, this invitation has turned out to convey more subversive intentions than it may have first appeared. Subversive of the ambient adversity – to forget problems, you dance – because in the course of its existence, *zouglou* claimed – and claims – to be the transformation of any adverse situation into an opportunity to laugh, hence the tone constantly shifting between laughter and tears, which is one of the most obvious markers of the practice. Subversive also through its tendency to confound a system represented by state violence, without overtly coming into contact with it. In fact, the overall tone may feel light-hearted, bordering on frivolous, but *zouglou* dance employs a parallel discourse that dramatically alters the connection between a somewhat latent antagonism and an open conflict in which the weakest opponent is not who they seem. In fact, while to all appearances the song, with its air of resignation, talks of students' helplessness faced with terrible living and studying conditions (“To the restau / it's only for dog / We don't like it / We'll eat all the same”), the discourse conveyed through dance provides yet another account and, without it ever being mentioned in the song, this disrupts all aspects of comprehension.

Hence, by inserting another existence into the discourse through the medium of dance, *zouglou* promotes an aesthetic of camouflage and ensnarement, present from the start and always controlled by the general climate in which the movement was born.

Censorship Against Censorship: The Founding Principles of *Pleurer-Rire*³⁹ Literature

Jonathan Pollock (2001) dedicated an essay to the definition of humour and its principles, maintaining that laughter, which stems from humour, cannot be understood without considering another phenomenon: melancholy. He believes that melancholy is manifested through a unique, macabre or morose joy, thereby entering the realm of humour. For him, these two notions mutually illuminate each other and are of one mind because they are born of a common sentiment, that of loss, which can also be a powerlessness to possess a being or a loved thing. So, humour can also mean mood, and both are simply unique forms of lucidity corresponding to “multiple layers of meaning”, from derisive and eccentric gaiety (hysterical

laughter) to melancholy (excess of black bile), which quite often stimulates tears. In other words, laughter and tears are two sides of the same coin and they express the same state of mind, but to different degrees and in different tones. From that, an increase in intellectual faculties emerges, correlating with an acute awareness of social phenomena, which, depending on circumstances, generates certain dispositions of the soul: sadness or melancholia, laughter and/or tears.

Controversial maybe, but these theories propose a potentially invisible but indestructible link between two notions that to all appearances are contradictory. And this link would have it that one cannot exist without the other. In a sense, this article's brief analysis of the zouglou discography in terms of content and tone appears to confirm these theories, and this is reinforced by the general idea of zouglou as a practice and philosophy that transforms chaotic situations into opportunities for joy. This situation establishes joy and affliction as the genre's driving forces, as well as their most immediate effects: laughter and tears, in constant opposition but inextricably linked. From this position certain recurrent representations converge that, as part of this practice, establish methods for signifying the hero in a dialectical and allegorical relationship that generates the representation of two oppositions: large and small, weak and strong. This disposition allows interpreters to examine each different register in turn. It also regularly, and indeed voluntarily, generates confusion in terms of content and the profound meaning of these songs. In fact, it is common to see that, through the intertwining of meanings and sounds, responding to each other and echoing each other, certain extracts seem to purposefully interfere with the reading/listening, as well as blurring the message and the often subversive and suppressed significance.

Ah tout va changer	Oh, everything will change
En tout cas tout doit changer	In any case, everything must change
Ah tout va changer	Oh, everything will change
En tout cas tout doit changer	In any case, everything must change
Ah tout va changer	In any case, everything must change
En tout cas tout doit changer	Oh, everything will change
Ah tout va changer	In any case, everything must change

<i>yé</i>	<i>yé</i> ⁴¹
<i>wa</i>	<i>wa</i> ⁴²
Arrêtez ça	Stop that
Nous on est fatigués ô:	We are tired ô:
<i>yé</i>	<i>yé</i>
<i>wa</i>	<i>wa</i>
Arrêtez ça	Stop that
Nous on est vaccinés ⁴⁰	We're big enough

In the second extract, it should be noted that while the interjections *yé* and *wa* are repeated in the same text, they deal with different semantic content when the linguistic context is taken into account. Thus punctuating the first verse with *yé* only has the same value when it returns in what we like to call the next “strophe”. Its first occurrence indeed refers to tears, the presence of the lexeme “*fatigué*” (tired) suggesting it is a call for help. Its second occurrence, in view of the lexeme “*vacciné*” (as in “*majeur et vacciné*”, meaning “big and ugly enough”), instead suggests a certain degree of weariness, irritation, even exasperation, which, at the same time, sounds like a thinly veiled threat. And there lies the subversion because it may give the impression of crying, but once interpreted, it announces outrage at an experience for which the end of the song foretells the demise or the vacuity (“Stop that / We are **tired** / Stop that / We’re **big enough**”).

The celebration/revendication of powerlessness allows zouglou performers to make light of the whole system, making fun of the supposed reigning powers to promote a society of underdogs.

By using self-deprecation as a form of expression, it reveals a form of resistance writing, which is all the more effective because it craftily renders the authors elusive and therefore non-submissive to censorship. Moreover, because he who cries tears claims his right to

existence, these tears – that have no basis in reality – can be seen as a desire for recognition and therefore for power. This demand is revolutionary in that, according to Séry Bailly (2009), by indicating that history is not yet finished, “it destabilises the social entity”. The shift thus accomplished necessitates a re-reading of present events because it looks ahead to a potential world, which changes the relationship between the individual and the group. Through tears and laughter, zouglou henceforth inserts and eases its way into a normality that calls for the guarantee of a better future. While highlighting revenge on society, this double perspective generates – and opens the door to – a reflection on the writing of literature, in that it allows a voice to be given to individuals that the system risked silencing forever.

Conclusion

Verbal or otherwise, zouglou text is written and creates its identity among others (genres, practices, discourses, etc.) like the source and horizon of new meaning. From this point of view, the practice, as initiated and promoted by the students, is opened up to meanings and critical analysis (these two aspects not being mutually exclusive). It exists as a discourse – in other words, as a group of texts considered and to consider in relation to their historical, sociological and ideological contexts of production, all of which determine (ideological) choices, (linguistic) wordplay and (literary) strategies from the outset. In the process of coding and interpreting, a highly revolutionary dual assertion arises.

On the one hand, the composition of these creations renders the discourse constructed in this way an activity that is both conditioned by its context and transformative of that same context, and here pertains to ideological subversion because the intention that underpins these phenomena shows that, facing the violence of the state, the reason of the weakest is sometimes the best.

On the other hand, inferring the idea of a code particular to zouglou, the claim of a particular linguistic domain that lays down norms, has an impact on the relationship of these young people to language and to one of its most accomplished manifestations: literature. And that relationship is not deficient, as some may have believed – far from it. In fact, it is expanding the spectrum of all we define as poetry, and we are thus called to, invited to, (re)think the increasingly outdated boundaries of literature, and to (re)question our perception of what is poetic and what is artistic.

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¹ Interview with Didier Bilé, Paris, 5 December 2005

² Translator’s note: A “*cité*” is a student residential area made up of purpose-built accommodation blocks, sometimes on a main campus but often at different sites around a university town or city.

³ The numerous available studies on zouglou orientate analysis towards issues of a historical and sociological nature and appear primarily in French (Tschiggfrey 1994; Yéré 2006; Eyoum-Ngangué 2009; Okomba 2009; Schumann 2010). They approach zouglou as a musical practice and take little interest in any consequent literary features. For the last two decades, I have moved against the tide to propose a literary, poetic identity for zouglou, whereby the formal constants are still to be identified (Adom 2000, 2012). The conclusions to this in-depth research, supported by a conference in 2014 (Adom 2018), have regularly served as an anchor point to other research publications (Lezou Koffi 2016, 2017, 2018, 2022; Lezou Koffi and Ouattara Adou 2020; Aghi Bahi 2011; Kossonou 2015), testifying to the importance of this genre, which nevertheless remains largely unknown in an Anglophone research context.

⁴ Office Ivoirien des Sports Scolaires et Universitaires (Ivorian Office for School and University Sports).

⁵ Interview with Didier Bilé, 2005.

⁶ In Côte d’Ivoire, Anango is a word used for the Yoruba people, an ethnic group primarily from Nigeria. The attached particle, *tchè* (from the Dioula language), indicates that the term is referring to someone of the masculine gender.

⁷ Interview with Ernest Nganza, 21 August 2005. Nganza is another zouglou pioneer.

⁸ Inspired by traditional singers, Wôyô is a music practice that still has a strong presence, even in present-day zouglou performances.

⁹ It is possible here that in the French he meant to say “secret” or “incognito”.

¹⁰ “Gboglo Koffi” is a song from the 1991 album *Ambiance Zougloutique* by Didier Bilé and Les Parents du Campus.

¹¹ Translator’s note: For clarity of argument, the translations of lyrics are literal but retain zouglou terms and references, which are explained by the author within the article itself or in notes. Stylistic features such as rhythm and rhyme can be read in the accompanying source text.

¹² At the time, Zinsou was the director of the Centre National des Œuvres Universitaires (National Centre for University Works), a student services and support centre.

¹³ Interview with Didier Bilé, 2005.

¹⁴ This is a parodic derivation of the word “*hasard*” in French, meaning chance or coincidence. The word refers to a term in martial arts, more precisely in judo. According to Wikipedia, waza-ari is obtained when an opponent falls on his back but the criteria for ippon are not reached, or when an opponent is immobilised for 15–20 seconds (in all categories). Playing on this sonorous approximation (paraphony), students created this derivation and used it in different ways to describe any situation that escapes common sense. The literary and ideological implications of this are developed later.

¹⁵ Interview with Didier Bilé, 2005.

¹⁶ More precisely, it was about numerous system dysfunctions that insidiously thrust students into hardship. The song mentioned here explains that co-payment meal tickets were not enough for them to eat satisfactorily and ease their hunger, among other things. It also highlights other issues, including overcrowded student buses and insufficient grants.

¹⁷ Interview with Didier Bilé, 2005.

¹⁸ Nouchi is the most well-known variety of French spoken in Côte d’Ivoire (though not the only variety). For more information on the mechanisms by which languages such as Nouchi convey meaning in an Ivorian context, see Adom (2016).

¹⁹ Interview with Didier Bilé, 2005.

²⁰ From the song “Campus” on the 1986 album entitled *Awoulaba* by Big Sat et l’Orchestre de l’Université d’Abidjan.

²¹ Kalet Bialey was the director of university works.

²² The name of a university restaurant.

²³ Nightclub on the Cocody university campus.

²⁴ Meaning “tickets restaurant”, i.e. meal vouchers.

²⁵ To court, to hit on someone (from Nouchi, constructed from the English root “break”).

²⁶ If someone is “*en pointage*”, they are introducing themselves to someone so as to make a move on them.

²⁷ The speech marks here indicate words spoken conversationally as opposed to the earlier section, which is sung.

²⁸ As explained above, wazari/waza-ari is ordinarily a score in judo; for students, this term is polysemous owing to its phonic proximity to the French word “*hasard*”, meaning chance or coincidence. It is therefore used to describe a situation that escapes all logic, so it can refer to disorder or incoherence. Here it is used to say that people are cooking any old thing, without really caring. Later, the term is used to describe zouglou dance steps, indicating that they are not just accidental, but instead are well thought through and convey meaning.

²⁹ Legend has it that one of the biggest student uprisings occurred because students had found “only for dog” written on couscous boxes in the university restaurant dustbins, and they concluded that this was what they had been given to eat.

³⁰ Otherwise known as Adowa in Ghana, or Kete, among the Bono people of Côte d’Ivoire, the dancers perform to the rhythms of different instruments. Some of these instruments, such as the atoungblan drums, are said to talk and use symbolic corporeal language to communicate maxims and/or short tales.

³¹ Interview with Didier Bilé, 2005.

³² For this zouglou step, the dancer performs a military salute.

³³ The dancer leans forward or to one side and pretends to pick up a stone; this gesture simulates the act of a student facing police repression, who tries to resist by throwing stones at the police, who were regularly called to university campuses during single-party rule.

³⁴ Along the same lines, this move consists of performing karate steps, representing the bravery of a student experienced in martial arts who alone would have knocked out two law enforcement officers during a police raid on a campus known for being particularly resistant to government instruction.

³⁵ Extract from “Gboglo Koffi”.

³⁶ Girl, young woman. Borrowed from the Nouchi lexicon, this word entered the French dictionary in 2022, alongside other words such as *boucancier* (artist/dancer in the *coupé-décalé* style, which draws from zouglou), *brouteur* (meaning both to effortlessly eat a lot and an online scammer) and *s’enjailler* (from Nouchi, but also from the similar-sounding English,

to enjoy). Preceded by a possessive, it means girlfriend or partner. So “Ma go” would be the equivalent of “my girlfriend”.

³⁷ Standing up in the bus; this expression is used as it evokes the image of medical students standing over their patients during visits to the sick or when carrying out procedures.

³⁸ Marcel Séaka. According to some sources, he composed this song. He is also considered to be one of the key thinkers behind the zouglou movement, thus providing it with conceptual content.

³⁹ *Le pleurer-rire* (The Laughing Cry) is a novel by Henri Lopes, considered to be an African literary classic. In it, he castigates the poor management of new powers arising from independence. The analyses that follow are in line with this critique of African powers and the forms of expression they could condition in African literatures, and the reference is made here to highlight the zouglou tone, forever oscillating between laughter and tears.

⁴⁰ Extract from “Arrêtez ça” (Stop That) by Espoir 2000.

⁴¹ Expression meaning “poor us”.

⁴² Onomatopoeia expressing tearfulness, desolation and disarray in this song. Like the previous expression, as well as *ô* and *lé* (which are used to emphasise the discourse), these locutions are abundant in zouglou songs and function as cries for help.